

The Prevalence and Incidence of Interstitial Lung Disease among Patients with Systemic Lupus Erythematosus: A Protocol for a Systematic Review

Registration:

The study is registered at PROSPERO. Registration number CRD420250642237

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First edition: 2025, 2nd of March

Before initiating the literature search etc., the systematic review will be registered with the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) guidelines (1).

In case of amendments regarding the protocol, the reason why, the data, and specific changes will be stated and described in an appendix.

Contributions

JKS is the guarantor and developer of the protocol. JKS will be doing the search and writing the manuscript. A health science librarian helped develop the search strategy. All authors were a part of developing the eligibility criteria and commented on the protocol.

JKS and HZL will screen articles and evaluate if the studies meet the eligibility criteria, perform data extraction and evaluate risk of bias, blinded to each other. Any discrepancy between JKS's and HZL's screening and selection of studies, will be settled by a discussion between JKS and HZL, and any disagreements will be settled by, a third person (AV).

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3/3-25
Joy Kiss Semmler, medical student

SUMMARY

Background

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic autoimmune disease, which can affect any organ systems and cause increased morbidity and mortality (2). Interstitial lung diseases (ILD) can manifest with heterogeneous radiological and pathological patterns in different categories of connective tissue diseases (CTD-ILD) including SLE (3). ILD is associated with reduced quality of life due to increased morbidity and mortality (3, 4). Diagnosing SLE-ILD is challenging, and the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD vary depending on the applied study methodology and study population (5-7). Clarifying an estimate of the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD will help clinicians' awareness of this rare disease presentation prompting an overall improved management including treatment plans.

Objective

The aims of this systematic review are to: i) estimate the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD and ii) report any possible difference in prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD between clinical- and register-based studies (includes studies based on registers or review of medical records, hereafter referred to as register-based studies).

Methods and Analysis

The protocol is developed in accordance with the PRISMA-P reporting guideline (1) (see Appendix A for checklist). The final article will be reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) reporting guideline (8). We will only include peer reviewed studies. The studies must meet the following eligibility criteria:

- Condition: Interstitial lung disease
- Context: Studies that examine the prevalence and/or incidence of SLE-ILD
- Population: Systemic lupus erythematosus patients

We will search in EMBASE (OVID), MEDLINE (OVID), Scopus and Cochrane Library and screen studies on basis of title and abstract. Studies that might meet the eligibility criteria will be

retrieved in full text and evaluated. Results will be recorded in a customized (pre-specified) Excel spreadsheet.

We will perform a systematic narrative synthesis based on the study results. We will also prepare a quantitative evidence synthesis (i.e. meta-analysis) of the prevalence and incidence in clinical studies and register-based studies if more than one study reports a prevalence and incidence. Thereafter, the studies will be analyzed for homogeneity/heterogeneity by I^2 -index and Forest plot.

Discussion

We believe that the forthcoming results of this study will clarify the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD. The results are expected to enhance the diagnosing of SLE-ILD, which ultimately could improve clinical outcomes.

Registration

The study is registered at PROSPERO. Registration number CRD420250642237

INTRODUCTION

Systemic lupus erythematosus is a chronic autoimmune disease, which can affect any organ system causing increased morbidity and mortality (2). The disease usually debuts among women between puberty and the menopause and the most frequent clinical manifestations are hematological abnormalities, skin manifestations, joint involvement and serositis (including pleuritis) (2). Pulmonary diseases are common among SLE patients and pleuritis is the most common manifestation. Interstitial lung disease is a more rare pulmonary manifestation in SLE, and can present itself as acute lupus pneumonitis, or a more slowly developing ILD (3).

Patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) and idiopathic fibrotic ILD have a poor prognosis with a survival rate of 3-5 years without treatment (4). Most often, treatment is available for patients with SLE related lung disease, which often results in improvement of symptoms and in some instances improve pulmonary function (9-11). Therefore, SLE-ILD seemingly having a superior prognosis compared to IPF (4). This underscores the importance of diagnosing SLE-ILD to prompt early treatment of SLE-ILD.

ILD manifestations can be difficult to diagnose in SLE and furthermore, the reported prevalence and incidence vary depending on study designs and study populations. A retrospective cohort study found that 31% of SLE patients had a lung disease, among whom 2% had diffuse ILD (5), while other studies have reported that the prevalence of SLE-ILD are up to 32% (6). In one study, the prevalence of SLE-ILD obtained from the patients' records, was 4% however increased to 16% after dedicated clinical investigations of SLE-ILD (7). This indicates that the prevalence of SLE-ILD varies with the study type.

To our knowledge, only one systematic review and meta-analysis has sought to estimate the prevalence and incidence of ILD among SLE patients (12), however, this study did not include several relevant studies (6, 7, 13, 14). As such, we aim to perform an updated systematic literature search including all relevant studies, in order to conduct a systematic review and, if possible, a meta-analysis, giving a more precise estimate of the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD.

In order for medical practitioners to accurately assess the risk of SLE-ILD, they must be aware of the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD. Therefore, gaining a more precise knowledge of how common SLE-ILD is, could help raise awareness of the risk of SLE-ILD, and hopefully improve patient outcomes.

Therefore, the aims of this systematic review are to: i) estimate the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD and ii) report any possible difference in prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD between clinical- and register-based studies.

Rationale for this evidence synthesis study

As described above, the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD vary between studies, and the only available systematic review on the subject did not include all relevant studies, which is why we believe that the prevalence of SLE-ILD is undefined (5-7, 12). When examining a SLE patient, it can therefore be difficult for the clinicians to know how much attention should be paid to potential ILD. Our hypothesis is that a more precise estimate of the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD, will increase awareness of SLE-ILD and hopefully improve patient outcomes.

Firstly, we find it important to give an estimate of the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD to know how much attention clinicians should pay to it, and possibly to dedicate sufficient resources to the topic.

Secondly, we find it important to investigate a possible difference in the prevalence and incidence of ILD among SLE patients in clinical studies and register-based studies, to know how to interpret results of such studies in the future.

Evidence-based research of existing knowledge in this field: We performed a pragmatic search for previous systematic reviews on 13. October 2024 reporting prevalence and incidence, ILD and SLE in Pubmed:

(SLE[tiab] OR lupus[tiab] OR "systemic lupus erythematosus"[tiab])

AND

(ILD[tiab] OR "interstitial lung diseas*" [tiab] OR lung*[tiab] OR pulmon*[tiab] OR respiratory[tiab])

AND

"systematic review*" [pt]

This search generated three potentially relevant review papers, which we scrutinized (out of 69 search results). One paper by Joy G.M. reported in a systematic review the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD (12). Apparently, at least four relevant studies were not included in the systematic review and meta-analysis (6, 7, 13, 14). Furthermore, half of the included studies included are not peer-reviewed.

Patient perspective

The protocol is discussed with a patient partner (SF). SF approves the protocol and study method. SF is aware of the importance of diagnosing SLE-ILD early for early treatment. SF finds it confusing, that there is no clear prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD. SF therefore claims, that it is relevant and important to find a more precise prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD.

METHODS

Protocol and registration

The study is registered at PROSPERO (CRD420250642237) and signed and uploaded on zenodo.org (3rd of March 2025)

Eligibility

The aim of the study is to determine the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD, which is why the CoCoPop (condition, context, population) framework for the systematic review is chosen (15, 16). Studies will be considered potentially eligible if they meet the following criteria:

- Condition: Interstitial lung disease
- Context: Clinical studies and register-based studies that examine the prevalence and/or incidence of SLE-ILD
- Population: Adults (≥ 18 years) diagnosed with SLE and fulfilling relevant classifications criteria at the time of the study

There will be no restriction on setting or time frame. Only peer reviewed studies will be included, to minimize the risk of including studies/abstracts with unclear study methods, and because we believe, that the peer review process are likely to improve methods of articles and remove mistakes in regards of results. Studies in English, Norwegian, Swedish, Danish and German will be included. A list of possible relevant titles in other languages will be provided in an appendix following the final manuscript.

Information sources and Search strategy

The literature search will be reported according to Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis for Searching (PRISMA-S)(17)(see appendix B for checklist) . The literature search will include both subject headings and free text search items. The search is developed under the guidance of a Health Science Librarian. All authors will be asked to contribute with comments to the search. There will be no limits or filters to the search. We will search EMBASE (OVID), MEDLINE (OVID), Scopus and Cochrane Library to find relevant studies (see appendix C for search).

After relevant studies are found, we will perform forward and backward citation search. We will use Web of Science for forward citation search, and if a study is not found in Web of Science, we will not perform any forward citation search. We will do backward citation search based on the references in the included articles. The search results will be valid for one year, and hereafter the search should be performed again for any updates. All references identified through the search will be uploaded and sorted in Covidence, where duplicates will be removed and afterwards, we will remove duplicates manually if any duplicates are found.

Study selection

JKS and HZL will independently and blinded of each other screen and select possible relevant references, on basis of abstracts and titles according to eligibility criteria.

Thereafter, independently and blinded of each other, JKS and HZL will evaluate the selected studies in full text and include those that meet the eligibility criteria.

Any discrepancy between JKS's and HZL's screening and inclusion of studies, will be settled by a discussion between JKS and HZL, and any disagreement will be settled by a third person (AV).

The reason for excluding studies reviewed in full text will be reported in an appendix. In addition, all authors will contribute additional studies if they are aware of relevant ones that have not been included. The selection of studies will be illustrated with a flow diagram in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Draft of flow chart, showing the selection of studies:

Data collection

Data will be extracted from the selected studies in a predefined customized Excel spreadsheet. This will be done by JKS and HZL, blinded to each other's results. Disagreements will be settled through a discussion between the two, and if necessary, settled by AV. The spreadsheet will include information on demography, methodology, population characteristics, selected risk factors for ILD, and the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD and, if available, subtype of SLE-ILD.

If data related to our primary or secondary outcomes are missing and/or has not been reported, the corresponding author will be contacted with up to three e-mails for supplementary information, to determine if the study meets the eligibility criteria and to include the missing information.

If the same study is reported in multiple papers, only the paper with the most comprehensive data to answer our research question will be included. The data mentioned below will be registered in a predefined document.

Data items

Following items will be extracted from the studies:

Study characteristics

- The studies: authors, publication year, reference, type of study, study size, country, inclusion period, number of centers, funding, publication status
- Study population: population, inclusion- and exclusion criteria, numbers of participants, characteristics (sex, age, activity index score, damage index score, smoking status, treatment, fitness level), how patients were diagnosed with SLE and the reason for dropouts in the study.

Results

- Parameters which have been used to diagnose/classify ILD in SLE patients
- The prevalence and incidence of ILD among SLE patients
- Subtypes on SLE-ILD

Risk of bias

Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies (QUADAS-2) (18) will be used to estimate risk of bias in each study. JKS and HZL will be addressing the risk of bias blinded to each other's results. Possible disagreements will be settled by a discussion between JKS and HZL, and if necessary, settled by AV. Risk of bias will be evaluated on patient selection, index test, reference standard, and flow and timing, which are the four key domains. The risk of reporting bias will be evaluated according to Outcome Reporting Bias in Trials (ORBIT)(19). After evaluating risk of reporting bias on outcomes, JKS and HZL will report an overall risk of reporting bias regarding our research question on study level. JKS and HZL will address the risk of reporting bias blinded to each other's results. Possible disagreements will be settled by a discussion between JKS and HZL, and if necessary, settled by AV.

Summary measures and synthesis of results

We will report the study characteristics as described above. Categorical variables will be presented as absolute (n) and relative measures (%). Continuous variables will be presented with a mean and standard deviation if normally distributed, or a median and a range if not normally distributed. We plan to do subgroup analyses grouping register-based studies and clinical studies. All p-values are two sided and we regard a significance level of 0.05 as significant.

We will perform a systematic narrative synthesis including text, tables and figures based on the study results. For each association, a quantitative evidence syntheses (i.e. meta-analysis) will be done if two or more studies report an outcome of interest as defined above. A random effect model will be used for the quantitative evidence syntheses. The quantitative results will be chosen to be as close as possible to an estimate of the target parameter. This is done to try to minimize the biases. If results are presented in different scales, they will be converted to a common format. Thereafter, the studies will be analyzed for heterogeneity by I^2 index and Forest plot. If $I^2 \geq 50\%$ the studies will be regarded heterogeneous. We plan to perform a sensitivity analyses, where we exclude all studies, where study participants are selected on basis of increased risk of SLE-ILD (for instance SLE patients with dyspnea or abnormal pulmonary function), to give the most precise estimate of the prevalence of SLE-ILD in unselected patients.

We will describe data and the primary outcome will be listed in a table. When secondary outcomes are reported, they will be listed in separate tables. The results will be reported independent of the risk of bias, but we will judge the evidence accordingly.

If any recommendations are to be made based on this study, we will evaluate the evidence behind with Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) (20).

DISCUSSION

It is important to be aware of SLE-ILD due to the associated morbidity and mortality, but unfortunately, we suspect that SLE-ILD is often overlooked. It might be due to the insidious nature of the symptoms or due to the fact that the prevalence and incidence vary between studies. On basis of a systematic review approach performed on clinical- and register-based studies, respectively, we aim to identify the prevalence and incidence of SLE-ILD and expect to be able to identify potential causes for variability in the ILD prevalence and incidence in different studies.

DISCLOSURES

None

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Mette Brandt Eriksen, SDU librarian, who helped developed the search. Als a special thanks to Sille Fløjborg, who volunteered to be patient partner in this study.

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Appendix A

PRISMA-P 2015 checklist: recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol*

Section and topic	Item No	Checklist item	Location(s) reported
ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION			
Title:			
Identification	1a	Identify the report as a protocol of a systematic review	<i>Title</i>
Update	1b	If the protocol is for an update of a previous systematic review, identify as such	<i>This is not a update</i>
Registration	2	If registered, provide the name of the registry (such as PROSPERO) and registration number	<i>Registration</i>
Authors:			
Contact	3a	Provide name, institutional affiliation, e-mail address of all protocol authors; provide physical mailing address of corresponding author	<i>Authors/collaborators Affiliations Corresponding author</i>
Contributions	3b	Describe contributions of protocol authors and identify the guarantor of the review	<i>Contributions</i>
Amendments	4	If the protocol represents an amendment of a previously completed or published protocol, identify as such and list changes; otherwise, state plan for documenting important protocol amendments	<i>First edition</i>
Support:			
Sources	5a	Indicate sources of financial or other support for the review	<i>No sources of financial or other support</i>
Sponsor	5b	Provide name for the review funder and/or sponsor	<i>No sponsor</i>
Role of sponsor or funder	5c	Describe roles of funder(s), sponsor(s), and/or institution(s), if any, in developing the protocol	<i>No sponsor</i>
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	6	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known	<i>Introduction</i>

			<i>Rationale for this evidence synthesis study</i>
Objectives	7	Provide an explicit statement of the question(s) the review will address with reference to participants, interventions, comparators, and outcomes (PICO)	<i>Introduction Eligibility</i>
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	8	Specify the study characteristics (such as PICO, study design, setting, time frame) and report characteristics (such as years considered, language, publication status) to be used as criteria for eligibility for the review	<i>Eligibility</i>
Information sources	9	Describe all intended information sources (such as electronic databases, contact with study authors, trial registers or other grey literature sources) with planned dates of coverage	<i>Information sources and search strategy Data collection</i>
Search strategy	10	Present draft of search strategy to be used for at least one electronic database, including planned limits, such that it could be repeated	<i>Information sources and search strategy Appendix C: Literature search</i>
Study records:			
Data management	11a	Describe the mechanism(s) that will be used to manage records and data throughout the review	<i>Information sources and search strategy Data collection</i>
Selection process	11b	State the process that will be used for selecting studies (such as two independent reviewers) through each phase of the review (that is, screening, eligibility and inclusion in meta-analysis)	<i>Study selection</i>
Data collection process	11c	Describe planned method of extracting data from reports (such as piloting forms, done independently, in duplicate), any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators	<i>Data collection</i>
Data items	12	List and define all variables for which data will be sought (such as PICO items, funding sources), any pre-planned data assumptions and simplifications	<i>Data items</i>
Outcomes and prioritization	13	List and define all outcomes for which data will be sought, including prioritization of main and additional outcomes, with rationale	<i>Introduction Rationale for this evidence synthesis study</i>

			<i>Data items</i>
Risk of bias in individual studies	14	Describe anticipated methods for assessing risk of bias of individual studies, including whether this will be done at the outcome or study level, or both; state how this information will be used in data synthesis	<i>Risk of bias</i>
Data synthesis	15a	Describe criteria under which study data will be quantitatively synthesised	<i>Summary measures and synthesis of results</i>
	15b	If data are appropriate for quantitative synthesis, describe planned summary measures, methods of handling data and methods of combining data from studies, including any planned exploration of consistency (such as I^2 , Kendall's τ)	<i>Summary measures and synthesis of results</i>
	15c	Describe any proposed additional analyses (such as sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression)	<i>Summary measures and synthesis of results</i>
	15d	If quantitative synthesis is not appropriate, describe the type of summary planned	<i>Summary measures and synthesis of results</i>
Meta-bias(es)	16	Specify any planned assessment of meta-bias(es) (such as publication bias across studies, selective reporting within studies)	<i>Risk of bias</i>
Confidence in cumulative evidence	17	Describe how the strength of the body of evidence will be assessed (such as GRADE)	<i>Summary measures and synthesis of results</i>

* It is strongly recommended that this checklist be read in conjunction with the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration (cite when available) for important clarification on the items. Amendments to a review protocol should be tracked and dated. The copyright for PRISMA-P (including checklist) is held by the PRISMA-P Group and is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution Licence 4.0.

From: Shamseer L, Moher D, Clarke M, Ghersi D, Liberati A, Petticrew M, Shekelle P, Stewart L, PRISMA-P Group. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *BMJ*. 2015 Jan 2;349(jan02 1):g7647.

Appendix B

PRISMA-S Checklist

Section/topic	#	Checklist item	Location(s) Reported
INFORMATION SOURCES AND METHODS			
Database name	1	Name each individual database searched, stating the platform for each.	<i>Information sources and search strategy</i>
Multi-database searching	2	If databases were searched simultaneously on a single platform, state the name of the platform, listing all of the databases searched.	<i>Not performed</i>
Study registries	3	List any study registries searched.	<i>Not performed</i>
Online resources and browsing	4	Describe any online or print source purposefully searched or browsed (e.g., tables of contents, print conference proceedings, web sites), and how this was done.	<i>Not performed</i>
Citation searching	5	Indicate whether cited references or citing references were examined, and describe any methods used for locating cited/citing references (e.g., browsing reference lists, using a citation index, setting up email alerts for references citing included studies).	<i>Information sources and search strategy</i>
Contacts	6	Indicate whether additional studies or data were sought by contacting authors, experts, manufacturers, or others.	<i>Data collection</i>
Other methods	7	Describe any additional information sources or search methods used.	<i>Study selection</i>
SEARCH STRATEGIES			
Full search strategies	8	Include the search strategies for each database and information source, copied and pasted exactly as run.	<i>Appendix C: Literature search</i>
Limits and restrictions	9	Specify that no limits were used, or describe any limits or restrictions applied to a search (e.g., date or time period, language, study design) and provide justification for their use.	<i>Information sources and search strategy</i>

Search filters	10	Indicate whether published search filters were used (as originally designed or modified), and if so, cite the filter(s) used.	<i>Information sources and search strategy</i>
Prior work	11	Indicate when search strategies from other literature reviews were adapted or reused for a substantive part or all of the search, citing the previous review(s).	<i>No prior work</i>
Updates	12	Report the methods used to update the search(es) (e.g., rerunning searches, email alerts).	<i>Information sources and search strategy</i>
Dates of searches	13	For each search strategy, provide the date when the last search occurred.	<i>Appendix C: Literature search</i>
PEER REVIEW			
Peer review	14	Describe any search peer review process.	<i>Information sources and search strategy</i>
MANAGING RECORDS			
Total Records	15	Document the total number of records identified from each database and other information sources.	<i>Appendix C: Literature search</i>
Deduplication	16	Describe the processes and any software used to deduplicate records from multiple database searches and other information sources.	<i>Information sources and search strategy</i>

PRISMA-S: An Extension to the PRISMA Statement for Reporting Literature Searches in Systematic Reviews
Rethlefsen ML, Kirtley S, Waffenschmidt S, Ayala AP, Moher D, Page MJ, Koffel JB, PRISMA-S Group.

Last updated February 27, 2020.

Appendix C

Literature Search:

- 1. EMBASE (OVID)**
- 2. MEDLINE (OVID)**
- 3. Cochrane Library**
- 4. Scopus**

1. EMBASE

Systemic lupus erythematosus

Subject headings:

Systemic lupus erythematosus

Acute lupus pneumonitis

Free text search items:

acute lupus pneumon* OR acute SLE pneumon* OR malignant dermatovisceritism* OR disseminated lupus OR erythematoses visceral* OR lupoviscerit* OR lupus erythematoses disseminat* OR lupus erythematosus disseminat* OR lupus erythematosus visceral* OR lupus pneumon* OR Osler Libman Sacks diseas* OR SLE OR systemic LE OR systemic lupus OR systemic lupus erythemato*

Interstitial lung disease

Subject headings:

Autoimmune lung disease

Bronchiolitis

Bronchiolitis obliterans

Bronchiolitis obliterans organizing pneumonia

Ground glass opacity

Interstitial lung disease

Chronic hypersensitivity pneumonitis

Fibrotic hypersensitivity pneumonitis

Connective tissue disease associated interstitial lung disease

Fibrosing alveolitis

Interstitial pneumonia

Lung alveolitis

Fibrosing alveolitis

Lung fibrosis

Combined pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema

Pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis

Fibrosing alveolitis

Reticular opacity

Organizing pneumonia

Free text search items:

autoimmune lung diseas* OR autoimmune pulmonary diseas* OR acute pneumon* OR alveolit* OR BOOP* OR bronchiolit* OR capillary bronchiolit* OR chronic diffuse interstitial fibros* OR chronic fibro* pneumon* OR chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon* OR chronic interstitial pneumon* OR CLAD obstructive phenotype* OR combined pulmonary fibrosis emphysem* OR constrictive bronchiolit* OR CPFE* OR cryptogenic organising pneumon* OR cryptogenic organizing pneumon* OR ILD* OR CTD-ILD* OR desquamative interstitial pneumon* OR (diffuse interstitial adj (fibros* OR pneumo* OR pulmon* fibros*)) OR diffuse parenchyma lung diseas* OR diffuse parenchymal lung diseas* OR (diffuse parenchymal pulmonary adj (diseas* OR disorder*)) OR diffuse pulmon* fibros* OR fibroid phthisis* OR fibro* hypersensitiv* pneumon* OR fibros* interstitial pneumon* OR fibros* pulmon* OR fibrotic* allergic pneumon* OR fibro* chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon* OR fibro* lung diseas* OR fibro* pulmon* diseas* OR GGO* OR ground glass opacities* OR (ground glass adj (attenuation* OR halo* OR nodule* OR opacification* OR opacity lesion* OR opacity nodule* OR pattern* OR shadow*)) OR (ground glasslike adj (appearance* OR change* OR lung lesion* OR opacity*)) OR (Hamman rich adj (diseas* OR syndrom*)) OR hypersensitiv* pneumon* OR idiopathic interstitial fibros* OR idiopathic pulmon* fibros* OR interstitial cell pneumon* OR (interstitial lung adj (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*)) OR interstitial* pneumon* OR (interstitial pulmonary adj (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*)) OR IPF* OR lung fibros* OR lung GGO* OR lung ground glass opacity* OR (lung adj (parenchymal fibros* OR reticulation* OR sclerosis*)) OR nonspecific interstitial pneumon* OR obliterated* bronchiolit* OR (obstructive chronic lung allograft adj (dysfunction* OR syndrom*)) OR obstructive CLAD* OR organizing pneumon* OR obstructive phenotype of chronic lung allograft syndrom* OR phthisis fibroidea* OR pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis* OR pneumosclerosis* OR (pulmon* adj (GGO* OR fibros*)) OR pulmon* sclerosis* OR (progressive fibros* interstitial adj (lung diseas* OR pulmon* diseas*)) OR PF-ILD* OR PPF* OR progressive pulmon* fibros* OR reticular lung opacity* OR reticular opacification*

EMBASE search history

Search History (17) ^		View Saved				
<input type="checkbox"/> # ▲ Searches	Results	Type	Actions	Annotations		
<input type="checkbox"/> 1	systemic lupus erythematosus/ or acute lupus pneumonitis/	131101	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 2	(acute lupus pneumon* or acute SLE pneumon* or malignant dermatovisceritism* or disseminated lupus or erythematodes visceral* or lupoviscerit* or lupus erythematodes disseminat* or lupus erythematosus disseminat* or lupus erythematosus visceral* or lupus pneumon* or Osler Libman Sacks disease* or SLE or systemic LE or systemic lupus or systemic lupus erythemato*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	155600	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 3	1 or 2	155600	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 4	autoimmune lung disease/	138	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 5	bronchiolitis/ or bronchiolitis obliterans/	25284	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 6	bronchiolitis obliterans/ or bronchiolitis obliterans organizing pneumonia/	9587	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 7	ground glass opacity/	12600	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 8	interstitial lung disease/ or chronic hypersensitivity pneumonitis/ or connective tissue disease associated interstitial lung disease/ or fibrosing alveolitis/ or interstitial pneumonia/	91235	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 9	chronic hypersensitivity pneumonitis/ or fibrotic hypersensitivity pneumonitis/	465	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 10	lung alveolitis/ or fibrosing alveolitis/	41650	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 11	lung fibrosis/ or "combined pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema"/ or fibrosing alveolitis/ or pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis/	86137	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 12	reticular opacity/	576	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 13	organizing pneumonia/	4048	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 14	4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13	169489	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 15	(autoimmune lung disease* or autoimmune pulmonary disease* or acute pneumon* or alveolit* or BOOP* or bronchiolit* or capillary bronchiolit* or chronic diffuse interstitial fibros* or chronic fibro* pneumon* or chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon* or chronic interstitial pneumon* or CLAD obstructive phenotype* or combined pulmonary fibrosis emphysem* or constrictive bronchiolit* or CPFE* or cryptogenic organising pneumon* or cryptogenic organizing pneumon* or ILD* or CTD-ILD* or desquamative interstitial pneumon* or (diffuse interstitial adj (fibros* or pneumo* or pulmon* fibros*)) or diffuse parenchyma lung disease* or diffuse parenchymal lung disease* or (diffuse parenchymal pulmonary adj (disease* or disorder*)) or diffuse pulmon* fibros* or fibroid phthisis* or fibro* hypersensitiv* pneumon* or fibros* interstitial pneumon* or fibros* pulmon* or fibrotic* allergic pneumon* or fibro* chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon* or fibro* lung disease* or fibro* pulmon* disease* or GGO* or ground glass opacities* or (ground glass adj (attenuation* or halo* or nodule* or opacification* or opacity lesion* or opacity nodule* or pattern* or shadow*)) or (ground glasslike adj (appearance* or change* or lung lesion* or opacity*)) or (Hamman rich adj (disease* or syndrom*)) or hypersensitiv* pneumon* or idiopathic interstitial fibros* or idiopathic pulmon* fibros* or interstitial cell pneumon* or (interstitial lung adj (disease* or disorder* or fibros*)) or interstitial* pneumon* or (interstitial pulmonary adj (disease* or disorder* or fibros*)) or IPF* or lung fibros* or lung GGO* or lung ground glass opacity* or (lung adj (parenchymal fibros* or reticulation* or sclerosis*)) or nonspecific interstitial pneumon* or obliterated* bronchiolit* or (obstructive chronic lung allograft adj (dysfunction* or syndrom*)) or obstructive CLAD* or organizing pneumon* or obstructive phenotype of chronic lung allograft syndrom* or phthisis fibroidea* or pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis* or pneumosclerosis* or (pulmon* adj (GGO* or fibros*)) or pulmon* sclerosis* or (progressive fibros* interstitial adj (lung disease* or pulmon* disease*)) or PF-ILD* or PPF* or progressive pulmon* fibros* or reticular lung opacity* or reticular opacification*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	213936	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 16	14 or 15	219649	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		
<input type="checkbox"/> 17	3 and 16	4379	Advanced	Display Results More ▾		

Results: 4379 (date: 2nd of March 2025)

2. MEDLINE

Systemic lupus erythematosus

Subject headings:

Systemic lupus erythematosus

Free text search items:

acute lupus pneumon* OR acute SLE pneumon* OR malignant dermatovisceritism* OR disseminated lupus OR erythematodes visceral* OR lupoviscerit* OR lupus erythematodes disseminat* OR lupus erythematosus disseminat* OR lupus erythematosus visceral* OR lupus pneumon* OR Osler Libman Sacks diseas* OR SLE OR systemic LE OR systemic lupus OR systemic lupus erythemato*

Interstitial lung disease

Subject headings:

Interstitial lung disease

Pulmonary Fibrosis

Free text search items:

autoimmune lung diseas* OR autoimmune pulmonary diseas* OR acute pneumon* OR alveolit* OR BOOP* OR bronchiolit* OR capillary bronchiolit* OR chronic diffuse interstitial fibros* OR chronic fibro* pneumon* OR chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon* OR chronic interstitial pneumon* OR CLAD obstructive phenotype* OR combined pulmonary fibrosis emphysem* OR constrictive bronchiolit* OR CPFE* OR cryptogenic organising pneumon* OR cryptogenic organizing pneumon* OR ILD* OR CTD-ILD* OR desquamative interstitial pneumon* OR (diffuse interstitial adj (fibros* OR pneumo* OR pulmon* fibros*)) OR diffuse parenchyma lung diseas* OR diffuse parenchymal lung diseas* OR (diffuse parenchymal pulmonary adj (diseas* OR disorder*)) OR diffuse pulmon* fibros* OR fibroid phthisis* OR fibro* hypersensitiv* pneumon* OR fibros* interstitial pneumon* OR fibros* pulmon* OR fibrotic* allergic pneumon* OR fibro* chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon* OR fibro* lung diseas* OR fibro* pulmon* diseas* OR GGO* OR ground glass opacities* OR (ground glass adj (attenuation* OR halo* OR nodule* OR opacification* OR opacity lesion* OR opacity nodule*

OR pattern* OR shadow*)) OR (ground glasslike adj (appearance* OR change* OR lung lesion* OR opacity*)) OR (Hamman rich adj (diseas* OR syndrom*)) OR hypersensitiv* pneumon* OR idiopathic interstitial fibros* OR idiopathic pulmon* fibros* OR interstitial cell pneumon* OR (interstitial lung adj (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*)) OR interstitial* pneumon* OR (interstitial pulmonary adj (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*)) OR IPF* OR lung fibros* OR lung GGO* OR lung ground glass opacity* OR (lung adj (parenchymal fibros* OR reticulation* OR sclerosis*)) OR nonspecific interstitial pneumon* OR obliterat* bronchiolit* OR (obstructive chronic lung allograft adj (dysfunction* OR syndrom*)) OR obstructive CLAD* OR organizing pneumon* OR obstructive phenotype of chronic lung allograft syndrom* OR phthisis fibroidea* OR pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis* OR pneumosclerosis* OR (pulmon* adj (GGO* OR fibros*)) OR pulmon* sclerosis* OR (progressive fibros* interstitial adj (lung diseas* OR pulmon* diseas*)) OR PF-ILD* OR PPF* OR progressive pulmon* fibros* OR reticular lung opacity* OR reticular opacification*

MEDLINE search history

Search History (7) ^		View Saved			
<input type="checkbox"/> # ▲ Searches	Results	Type	Actions	Annotations	
<input type="checkbox"/> 1	Lupus Erythematosus, Systemic/	64266	Advanced	Display Results More	
<input type="checkbox"/> 2	(acute lupus pneumon* or acute SLE pneumon* or malignant dermatovisceritism* or disseminated lupus or erythematoses visceral* or lupoviscerit* or lupus erythematoses disseminat* or lupus erythematosus disseminat* or lupus erythematosus visceral* or lupus pneumon* or Osler Libman Sacks diseas* or SLE or systemic LE or systemic lupus or systemic lupus erythemato*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	74210	Advanced	Display Results More	
<input type="checkbox"/> 3	1 or 2	89644	Advanced	Display Results More	
<input type="checkbox"/> 4	lung diseases, interstitial/ or pulmonary fibrosis/	34902	Advanced	Display Results More	
<input type="checkbox"/> 5	(autoimmune lung diseas* or autoimmune pulmonary diseas* or acute pneumon* or alveolit* or BOOP* or bronchiolit* or capillary bronchiolit* or chronic diffuse interstitial fibros* or chronic fibro* pneumon* or chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon* or chronic interstitial pneumon* or CLAD obstructive phenotype* or combined pulmonary fibrosis emphysem* or constrictive bronchiolit* or CPFE* or cryptogenic organising pneumon* or cryptogenic organizing pneumon* or ILD* or CTD-ILD* or desquamative interstitial pneumon* or (diffuse interstitial adj (fibros* or pneumo* or pulmon* fibros*)) or diffuse parenchyma lung diseas* or diffuse parenchymal lung diseas* or (diffuse parenchymal pulmonary adj (diseas* or disorder*)) or diffuse pulmon* fibros* or fibroid phthisis* or fibro* hypersensitiv* pneumon* or fibros* interstitial pneumon* or fibros* pulmon* or fibrotic* allergic pneumon* or fibro* chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon* or fibro* lung diseas* or fibro* pulmon* diseas* or GGO* or ground glass opacities* or (ground glass adj (attenuation* or halo* or nodule* or opacification* or opacity lesion* or opacity nodule* or pattern* or shadow*)) or (ground glasslike adj (appearance* or change* or lung lesion* or opacity*)) or (Hamman rich adj (diseas* or syndrom*)) or hypersensitiv* pneumon* or idiopathic interstitial fibros* or idiopathic pulmon* fibros* or interstitial cell pneumon* or (interstitial lung adj (diseas* or disorder* or fibros*)) or interstitial* pneumon* or (interstitial pulmonary adj (diseas* or disorder* or fibros*)) or IPF* or lung fibros* or lung GGO* or lung ground glass opacity* or (lung adj (parenchymal fibros* or reticulation* or sclerosis*)) or nonspecific interstitial pneumon* or obliterat* bronchiolit* or (obstructive chronic lung allograft adj (dysfunction* or syndrom*)) or obstructive CLAD* or organizing pneumon* or obstructive phenotype of chronic lung allograft syndrom* or phthisis fibroidea* or pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis* or pneumosclerosis* or (pulmon* adj (GGO* or fibros*)) or pulmon* sclerosis* or (progressive fibros* interstitial adj (lung diseas* or pulmon* diseas*)) or PF-ILD* or PPF* or progressive pulmon* fibros* or reticular lung opacity* or reticular opacification*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]	103170	Advanced	Display Results More	
<input type="checkbox"/> 6	4 or 5	105053	Advanced	Display Results More	
<input type="checkbox"/> 7	3 and 6	1084	Advanced	Display Results More	

Results: 1084 (date: 2nd of March 2025)

3. Cochrane Library

Systemic lupus erythematosus

MESH terms

Lupus Erythematosus, Systemic

Free text search items:

(acute NEXT lupus NEXT pneumon*) OR (acute NEXT SLE NEXT pneumon*) OR (malignant NEXT dermatovisceritism*) OR (disseminated NEXT lupus) OR (erythematoses NEXT visceral*) OR (lupoviscerit*) OR (lupus NEXT erythematoses NEXT disseminat*) OR (lupus NEXT erythematosus NEXT disseminat*) OR (lupus NEXT erythematosus NEXT visceral*) OR (lupus NEXT pneumon*) OR (Osler NEXT Libman NEXT Sacks NEXT diseas*) OR (SLE) OR (systemic NEXT LE) OR (systemic NEXT lupus) OR (systemic NEXT lupus NEXT erythemato*)

Interstitial lung disease

MESH terms

Lung Diseases, Interstitial

Pulmonary Fibrosis

Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis

Hamman-Rich Syndrome

Idiopathic Interstitial Pneumonias

Cryptogenic Organizing Pneumonia

Free text search items:

(autoimmune NEXT lung NEXT diseas*) OR (autoimmune NEXT pulmonary NEXT diseas*) OR (acute NEXT pneumon*) OR (alveolit*) OR (BOOP*) OR (bronchiolit*) OR (capillary NEXT bronchiolit*) OR (chronic NEXT diffuse NEXT interstitial NEXT fibros*) OR (chronic NEXT fibro* NEXT pneumon*) OR (chronic NEXT hypersensitiv* NEXT pneumon*) OR (chronic NEXT interstitial NEXT pneumon*) OR (CLAD NEXT obstructive NEXT phenotyp*) OR (combined NEXT pulmonary NEXT fibrosis NEXT emphysem*) OR (constrictive NEXT bronchiolit*) OR (CPFE*) OR (cryptogenic NEXT organising NEXT pneumon*) OR (cryptogenic

NEXT organizing NEXT pneumon*) OR (ILD*) OR (CTD-ILD*) OR (desquamative NEXT
interstitial NEXT pneumon*) OR ((diffuse NEXT interstitial) NEAR (fibros* OR pneumo* OR
(pulmon* NEXT fibros*))) OR (diffuse NEXT parenchyma NEXT lung NEXT diseas*) OR
(diffuse NEXT parenchymal NEXT lung NEXT diseas*) OR ((diffuse NEXT parenchymal NEXT
pulmonary) NEAR (diseas* OR disorder*)) OR (diffuse NEXT pulmon* NEXT fibros*) OR
(fibroid NEXT phthisis*) OR (fibro* NEXT hypersensitiv* NEXT pneumon*) OR (fibros* NEXT
interstitial NEXT pneumon*) OR (fibros* NEXT pulmon*) OR (fibrotic* NEXT allergic NEXT
pneumon*) OR (fibro* NEXT chronic NEXT hypersensitiv* NEXT pneumon*) OR (fibro* NEXT
lung NEXT diseas*) OR (fibro* NEXT pulmon* NEXT diseas*) OR (GGO*) OR (ground NEXT
glass NEXT opacities*) OR ((ground NEXT glass) NEAR (attenuation* OR halo* OR nodule* OR
opacification* OR (opacity NEXT lesion*) OR (opacity NEXT nodule*) OR pattern* OR
shadow*)) OR ((ground NEXT glasslike) NEAR (appearance* OR change* OR (lung NEXT
lesion*) OR opacity*)) OR ((Hamman NEXT rich) NEAR (diseas* OR syndrom*)) OR
(hypersensitiv* NEXT pneumon*) OR (idiopathic NEXT interstitial NEXT fibros*) OR
(idiopathic NEXT pulmon* NEXT fibros*) OR (interstitial NEXT cell NEXT pneumon*) OR
((interstitial NEXT lung) NEAR (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*)) OR (interstitial* NEXT
pneumon*) OR ((interstitial NEXT pulmonary) NEAR (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*)) OR
(IPF*) OR (lung NEXT fibros*) OR (lung NEXT GGO*) OR (lung NEXT ground NEXT glass NEXT
opacity*) OR ((lung) NEAR ((parenchymal NEXT fibros*) OR reticulation* OR sclerosis*)) OR
(nonspecific NEXT interstitial NEXT pneumon*) OR (obliterat* NEXT bronchiolit*) OR
((obstructive NEXT chronic NEXT lung NEXT allograft) NEAR (dysfunction* OR syndrom*))
OR (obstructive NEXT CLAD*) OR (organizing NEXT pneumon*) OR (obstructive NEXT
phenotype NEXT of NEXT chronic NEXT lung NEXT allograft NEXT syndrom*) OR (phthisis
NEXT fibroidea*) OR (pleuroparenchymal NEXT fibroelastosis*) OR (pneumosclerosis*) OR
((pulmon*) NEAR (GGO* OR fibros*)) OR (pulmon* NEXT sclerosis*) OR ((progressive NEXT
fibros* NEXT interstitial) NEAR ((lung NEXT diseas*) OR (pulmon* NEXT diseas*))) OR (PF-
ILD*) OR (PPF*) OR (progressive NEXT pulmon* NEXT fibros*) OR (reticular NEXT lung NEXT
opacity*) OR (reticular NEXT opacification*)

Cochrane Library search history

-	+	#1	MeSH descriptor: [Lupus Erythematosus, Systemic] this term only	MeSH ▾	1303	
-	+	#2	((acute NEXT lupus NEXT pneumon*) OR (acute NEXT SLE NEXT pneumon*) OR (malignant NEXT dermatovisceritism*) OR (disseminated NEXT lupus) OR (erythematodes NEXT visceral*) OR (lupoviscerit*) OR (lupus NEXT erythematodes NEXT disseminat*) OR (lupus NEXT erythematosus NEXT disseminat*) OR (lupus NEXT erythematosus NEXT visceral*) OR (lupus NEXT pneumon*) OR (Osler NEXT Libman NEXT Sacks NEXT diseas*) OR (SLE) OR (systemic NEXT LE) OR (systemic NEXT lupus) OR (systemic NEXT lupus NEXT erythemato*)):ti,ab,kw	S ▾	Limits	3495
-	+	#3	MeSH descriptor: [Lung Diseases, Interstitial] this term only	MeSH ▾	523	
-	+	#4	MeSH descriptor: [Pulmonary Fibrosis] this term only	MeSH ▾	585	
-	+	#5	MeSH descriptor: [Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis] this term only	MeSH ▾	579	
-	+	#6	MeSH descriptor: [Hamman-Rich Syndrome] this term only	MeSH ▾	2	
-	+	#7	MeSH descriptor: [Idiopathic Interstitial Pneumonias] this term only	MeSH ▾	108	
-	+	#8	MeSH descriptor: [Cryptogenic Organizing Pneumonia] this term only	MeSH ▾	6	
-	+	#9	((autoimmune NEXT lung NEXT diseas*) OR (autoimmune NEXT pulmonary NEXT diseas*) OR (acute NEXT pneumon*) OR (alveolit*) OR (BOOP*) OR (bronchiolit*) OR (capillary NEXT bronchiolit*) OR (chronic NEXT diffuse NEXT interstitial NEXT fibros*) OR (chronic NEXT fibro* NEXT pneumon*) OR (chronic NEXT hypersensitiv* NEXT pneumon*) OR (chronic NEXT interstitial NEXT pneumon*) OR (CLAD NEXT obstructive NEXT phenotype*) OR (combined NEXT pulmonary NEXT fibrosis NEXT emphysem*) OR (constrictive NEXT bronchiolit*) OR (CPFE*) OR (cryptogenic NEXT organising NEXT pneumon*) OR (cryptogenic NEXT organizing NEXT pneumon*) OR (ILD*) OR (CTD-ILD*) OR (desquamative NEXT interstitial NEXT pneumon*) OR ((diffuse NEXT interstitial) NEAR (fibros* OR pneumo* OR (pulmon* NEXT fibros*))) OR (diffuse NEXT parenchyma NEXT lung NEXT diseas*) OR (diffuse NEXT parenchymal NEXT lung NEXT diseas*) OR (diffuse NEXT parenchymal NEXT pulmonary) NEAR (diseas* OR disorder*)) OR (diffuse NEXT pulmon* NEXT fibros*) OR (fibroid NEXT phthisis*) OR (fibro* NEXT hypersensitiv* NEXT pneumon*) OR (fibros* NEXT interstitial NEXT pneumon*) OR (fibros* NEXT pulmon*) OR (fibrotic* NEXT allergic NEXT pneumon*) OR (fibro* NEXT chronic NEXT hypersensitiv* NEXT pneumon*) OR (fibro* NEXT lung NEXT diseas*) OR (fibro* NEXT pulmon* NEXT diseas*) OR (GGO*) OR (ground NEXT glass NEXT opacities*) OR ((ground NEXT glass) NEAR (attenuation* OR halo* OR nodule* OR opacification* OR (opacity NEXT lesion*) OR (opacity NEXT nodule*) OR pattern* OR shadow*)) OR ((ground NEXT glasslike) NEAR (appearance* OR change* OR (lung NEXT lesion*) OR opacity*)) OR ((Hamman NEXT rich) NEAR (diseas* OR syndrom*)) OR (hypersensitiv* NEXT pneumon*) OR (idiopathic NEXT interstitial NEXT fibros*) OR (idiopathic NEXT pulmon* NEXT fibros*) OR (interstitial NEXT cell NEXT pneumon*) OR ((interstitial NEXT lung) NEAR (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*)) OR (interstitial* NEXT pneumon*) OR ((interstitial NEXT pulmonary) NEAR (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*)) OR (IPF*) OR (lung NEXT fibros*) OR (lung NEXT GGO*) OR (lung NEXT ground NEXT glass NEXT opacity*) OR ((lung) NEAR ((parenchymal NEXT fibros*) OR reticulation* OR sclerosis*)) OR (nonspecific NEXT interstitial NEXT pneumon*) OR (obliterat* NEXT bronchiolit*) OR ((obstructive NEXT chronic NEXT lung NEXT allograft) NEAR (dysfunction* OR syndrom*)) OR (obstructive NEXT CLAD*) OR (organizing NEXT pneumon*) OR (obstructive NEXT phenotype NEXT of NEXT chronic NEXT lung NEXT allograft NEXT syndrom*) OR (phthisis NEXT fibroidea*) OR (pleuroparenchymal NEXT fibroelastosis*) OR (pneumosclerosis*) OR ((pulmon*) NEAR (GGO* OR fibros*)) OR (pulmon* NEXT sclerosis*) OR ((progressive NEXT fibros* NEXT interstitial) NEAR ((lung NEXT diseas*) OR (pulmon* NEXT diseas*))) OR (PF-ILD*) OR (PPF*) OR (progressive NEXT pulmon* NEXT fibros*) OR (reticular NEXT lung NEXT opacity*) OR (reticular NEXT opacification*)):ti,ab,kw	S ▾	Limits	8281
-	+	#10	#1 or #2	Limits	3624	
-	+	#11	#3 or #4 or #5 or #6 or #7 or #8 or #9	Limits	8332	
-	+	#12	#10 and #11	Limits	32	

Results: 32 trials (date: 2nd of March 2025)

4. SCOPUS

Systemic lupus erythematosus

Free text search items:

“acute lupus pneumon*” OR “acute SLE pneumon*” OR “malignant dermatovisceritism*” OR “disseminated lupus” OR “erythematoses visceral*” OR “lupoviscerit*” OR “lupus erythematoses disseminat*” OR “lupus erythematosus disseminat*” OR “lupus erythematosus visceral*” OR “lupus pneumon*” OR “Osler Libman Sacks diseas*” OR “SLE” OR “systemic LE” OR “systemic lupus” OR “systemic lupus erythemato*”

Interstitial lung disease

Free text search items:

“autoimmune lung diseas*” OR “autoimmune pulmonary diseas*” OR “acute pneumon*” OR “alveolit*” OR “BOOP*” OR “bronchiolit*” OR “capillary bronchiolit*” OR “chronic diffuse interstitial fibros*” OR “chronic fibro* pneumon*” OR “chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon*” OR “chronic interstitial pneumon*” OR “CLAD obstructive phenotype*” OR “combined pulmonary fibrosis emphysem*” OR “constrictive bronchiolit*” OR “CPFE*” OR “cryptogenic organising pneumon*” OR “cryptogenic organizing pneumon*” OR “ILD*” OR “CTD-ILD*” OR “desquamative interstitial pneumon*” OR “(diffuse interstitial W/0 (fibros* OR pneumo* OR pulmon* fibros*))” OR “diffuse parenchyma lung diseas*” OR “diffuse parenchymal lung diseas*” OR “(diffuse parenchymal pulmonary W/0 (diseas* OR disorder*))” OR “diffuse pulmon* fibros*” OR “fibroid phthisis*” OR “fibro* hypersensitiv* pneumon*” OR “fibros* interstitial pneumon*” OR “fibros* pulmon*” OR “fibrotic* allergic pneumon*” OR “fibro* chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon*” OR “fibro* lung diseas*” OR “fibro* pulmon* diseas*” OR “GGO*” OR “ground glass opacities*” OR “(ground glass W/0 (attenuation* OR halo* OR nodule* OR opacification* OR opacity lesion* OR opacity nodule* OR pattern* OR shadow*))” OR “(ground glasslike W/0 (appearance* OR change* OR lung lesion* OR opacity*))” OR “(Hamman rich W/0 (diseas* OR syndrom*))” OR “hypersensitiv* pneumon*” OR “idiopathic interstitial fibros*” OR “idiopathic pulmon* fibros*” OR “interstitial cell pneumon*” OR “(interstitial lung W/0 (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*))” OR “interstitial* pneumon*” OR “(interstitial pulmonary W/0 (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*))” OR “IPF*” OR “lung fibros*”

OR "lung GGO*" OR "lung ground glass opacity*" OR "(lung W/0 (parenchymal fibros* OR reticulation* OR sclerosis*))" OR "nonspecific interstitial pneumon*" OR "obliterat* bronchiolit*" OR "(obstructive chronic lung allograft W/0 (dysfunction* OR syndrom*))" OR "obstructive CLAD*" OR "organizing pneumon*" OR "obstructive phenotype of chronic lung allograft syndrom*" OR "phthisis fibroidea*" OR "pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis*" OR "pneumosclerosis*" OR "(pulmon* W/0 (GGO* OR fibros*))" OR "pulmon* sclerosis*" OR "(progressive fibros* interstitial W/0 (lung diseas* OR pulmon* diseas*))" OR "PF-ILD*" OR "PPF*" OR "progressive pulmon* fibros*" OR "reticular lung opacity*" OR "reticular opacification*"

Scopus search history

(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("acute lupus pneumon*" OR "acute SLE pneumon*" OR "malignant dermatovisceritism*" OR "disseminated lupus" OR "erythematodes visceral*" OR "lupoviscerit*" OR "lupus erythematodes disseminat*" OR "lupus erythematosus disseminat*" OR "lupus erythematosus visceral*" OR "lupus pneumon*" OR "Osler Libman Sacks diseas*" OR "SLE" OR "systemic LE" OR "systemic lupus" OR "systemic lupus erythemato*")

AND

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("autoimmune lung diseas*" OR "autoimmune pulmonary diseas*" OR "acute pneumon*" OR "alveolit*" OR "BOOP*" OR "bronchiolit*" OR "capillary bronchiolit*" OR "chronic diffuse interstitial fibros*" OR "chronic fibro* pneumon*" OR "chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon*" OR "chronic interstitial pneumon*" OR "CLAD obstructive phenotype*" OR "combined pulmonary fibrosis emphysem*" OR "constrictive bronchiolit*" OR "CPFE*" OR "cryptogenic organising pneumon*" OR "cryptogenic organizing pneumon*" OR "ILD*" OR "CTD-ILD*" OR "desquamative interstitial pneumon*" OR "(diffuse interstitial W/0 (fibros* OR pneumo* OR pulmon* fibros*))" OR "diffuse parenchyma lung diseas*" OR "diffuse parenchymal lung diseas*" OR "(diffuse parenchymal pulmonary W/0 (diseas* OR disorder*))" OR "diffuse pulmon* fibros*" OR "fibroid phthisis*" OR "fibro* hypersensitiv* pneumon*" OR "fibros* interstitial pneumon*" OR "fibros* pulmon*" OR "fibrotic* allergic pneumon*" OR "fibro* chronic hypersensitiv* pneumon*" OR "fibro* lung diseas*" OR "fibro* pulmon* diseas*" OR "GGO*" OR "ground glass opacities*" OR "(ground glass W/0 (attenuation* OR halo* OR nodule* OR opacification* OR opacity lesion* OR opacity nodule* OR pattern* OR shadow*))" OR "(ground glasslike W/0 (appearance* OR change* OR lung lesion* OR opacity*))" OR "(Hamman rich W/0 (diseas* OR syndrom*))" OR "hypersensitiv* pneumon*" OR "idiopathic interstitial fibros*" OR "idiopathic pulmon* fibros*" OR "interstitial cell pneumon*" OR "(interstitial lung W/0 (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*))" OR "interstitial* pneumon*" OR "(interstitial pulmonary W/0 (diseas* OR disorder* OR fibros*))" OR "IPF*" OR "lung fibros*" OR "lung GGO*" OR "lung ground glass opacity*" OR "(lung W/0 (parenchymal fibros* OR reticulation* OR sclerosis*))" OR "nonspecific interstitial pneumon*")

OR "obliterat* bronchiolit*" OR "(obstructive chronic lung allograft W/0 (dysfunction* OR syndrom*))" OR "obstructive CLAD*" OR "organizing pneumon*" OR "obstructive phenotype of chronic lung allograft syndrom*" OR "phthisis fibroidea*" OR "pleuroparenchymal fibroelastosis*" OR "pneumosclerosis*" OR "(pulmon* W/0 (GGO* OR fibros*))" OR "pulmon* sclerosis*" OR "(progressive fibros* interstitial W/0 (lung diseas* OR pulmon* diseas*))" OR "PF-ILD*" OR "PPF*" OR "progressive pulmon* fibros*" OR "reticular lung opacity*" OR "reticular opacification*"))

Results: 2210 (date: 2nd of March 2025)